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Low Power Phase Change Memory Switching of Ultra-Thin $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ Nanowires

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ABSTRACT

We report on the fabrication and electrical characterization of phase change memory (PCM) devices formed by $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ chalcogenide nanowires (NWs), with diameters as small as 20 nm. The NWs were self-assembled by metal organic chemical vapor deposition via the vapor-liquid-solid method, catalyzed by Au nanoparticles. Reversible and well reproducible memory switching of the NWs between low and high resistance states was demonstrated. The conduction mechanism of the high resistance state was investigated according to a trap-limited model for electrical transport in the amorphous phase. The size of the amorphized portion of the NW and the critical

electric field for the transition to the low resistance state were evaluated. The $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NW-based devices showed very low working parameters, such as RESET voltage (~ 3 V), current (~ 40 μA) and power (~ 130 μW). Our results indicated that the studied NWs are suitable candidates for the realization of ultra-scaled, high performance PCM devices.

In recent years, the interest for the development of a new class of memories, the Storage Class Memory (SCM), has greatly increased [1]. The SCM would fill the gap between “operation” memory (DRAM) and “storage” memory (Flash and/or hard disk drive). Possible SCM candidates should be based on non-volatile memory cells, much faster and with higher endurance than Flash devices, and have high density and reasonably low cost/bit [2]. Phase Change Memories (PCMs) are promising constituents for SCM, due to their fast switching, inherent scalability, high device endurance and relatively long data retention time [3]. Currently, the main limitations of PCMs are the somehow inadequate thermal stability, affecting the retention time, and the relatively high amorphization (RESET) currents. Typical technological implementations of PCM devices are generally based on a heater/chalcogenide thin film architecture and exploit alloys of the pseudo-binary line between Sb_2Te_3 and GeTe [4], such as $\text{Ge}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_5$. To overcome the current limitations of PCMs, the investigation of different phase change materials and the development of devices employing innovative nanostructures are required. The use of chalcogenide nanowires (NWs) is a particularly appealing solution, allowing a tremendous downscaling of the cell size, and hence to reach higher memory densities. Moreover, compared to conventional PCMs, NWs have been shown to exhibit more efficient phase change transition

processes and, in particular, a reduced RESET power. The self-heating approach is expected to be the most efficient for PCM applications [5] and does not require special heater-electrodes, as the heat generation occurs directly within the chalcogenide material. However, it implies a risky technological implementation, due to the high aspect-ratio that is needed for the involved nanostructures. Self-assembled NWs normally present a sufficiently high aspect ratio, along with extremely small diameters, particularly suitable for the self-heating mechanism. Moreover, NWs grown by bottom-up techniques turn out to be typically defect-free structures, whereas the conventional top-down approach with multiple lithographic and etching steps generally leads to structural/chemical degradation of the phase-change materials, which is detrimental to the high scalability, low power consumption and non-volatility requirements. While the physical mechanisms of electrical resistance variations in NWs are still under debate [6]–[8], the reduction of the writing currents has been demonstrated in $\text{Ge}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_5$ and GeTe NW-based PCM cells [9], [10]. On the other hand, recrystallization studies have shown a diminution of activation energies and data retention times depending on the NW diameter [9]. One possibility to counteract this effect is given by the use of In-Sb-Te chalcogenide alloys, such as $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$, which exhibit a higher crystallization temperature ($>290\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) with respect to Ge-Sb-Te alloys [11]–[13]. In-Sb-Te PCM cells based on thin films have been fabricated and characterized, demonstrating good resistance contrast, high endurance and multiple resistance levels [14], [15]. The phase change functioning of $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NWs has also been reported in [16]. However, in these works much higher RESET voltage values than those employed in industrial implementations of PCMs were observed. Here we report on the low-power and low-programming voltage phase change properties of ultra-thin $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NWs, grown by MOCVD coupled to the VLS mechanism [17].

The growth of the $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NWs was performed by an Aixtron® AIX 200/4 MOCVD reactor. The NWs were self-assembled on 1 cm^2 Si(100) substrates, after removal of the native oxide by immersion in an HF 5% solution, on which the catalyst Au nanoparticles for VLS with a diameter of 10 nm were deposited by a colloidal solution supplied by British Bio Cell Company®, according to the procedure described in [18]. The used metalorganic precursors were electronic grade dimethylaminopropyldimethylindium ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_{18}\text{InN}$), antimonytrichloride (SbCl_3) and bis(trimethylsilyl)telluride ($\text{Te}(\text{SiMe}_3)_2$), provided by Air Liquide®. The optimization of the growth parameters, discussed in [17], led to the synthesis of $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NWs, with diameters down to 14 nm and lengths of a few microns.

Figure 1: HRTEM image of a 14 nm thick $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NW. (b) Enlargement of the white squared region showing the atomic arrangement of the rock salt phase in the $[-111]$ projection and (c) its FFT.

High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM), performed in a field emission JEOL® 2200FS microscope, equipped with X-Ray microanalysis (EDX), showed that the NWs grow in the rock salt phase of $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$. Notably, the NWs appear to be perfect crystals, as no extended defects were observed. Figure 1(a) shows a HRTEM image of a 14 nm thick $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NW. The atomic arrangement is clearly visible in the higher magnification image of Figure 1(b). The lattice spacing of the atomic planes along the growth direction was measured to

be 0.217 nm, which is compatible with the $\{220\}$ planes of the $Fm\bar{3}m$ structure of the $In_3Sb_1Te_2$ [17]. This indication is further confirmed by the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) reported in Figure 1(c): the NW is oriented along the $[-111]$ zone axis, thus showing the six identical $\{220\}$ reflections.

Figure 2: Tilted SEM image of the PCM device formed by a $In_3Sb_1Te_2$ NW, contacted by Ni/Au micro-electrodes fabricated on top of the NW by EBL.

For the electrical characterization, NWs were dry-transferred onto insulating substrates with pre-patterned macro-pads and two-terminal devices were fabricated using Electron Beam Lithography (EBL). A 270 nm thick layer of PMMA AR-P 679.04 was spin-coated and baked at 180 °C, following which EBL of the connection tracks and nano-contacts, metallization (Ni/Au: 20/100 nm) and lift-off were performed (Figure 2). The electrical properties of the $In_3Sb_1Te_2$ NWs were investigated by the Transmission Line Pulse (TLP) technique [19], using a HPPI ® system. In particular, the measurement set-up consisted of a 50 Ω high voltage pulse generator, a high speed digital oscilloscope, a Source Meter Unit (SMU) and a control computer. The differential voltage was measured directly at the fabricated devices by the four-point Kelvin method. In order

to measure the device resistance, direct current (d.c.) measurements in the pA ÷ mA range were performed after each pulse, using the switch configuration with the SMU. The described TLP system allowed producing pulses with a fine control on their amplitude and shape. In particular, it was possible to realize a very fast pulse falling time, which is crucial for the amorphization of phase change materials, because a rapid quenching is required to avoid recrystallization. The inset in Figure 3 shows a representative RESET pulse with a voltage amplitude of 3 V, a duration of 100 ns and a falling time of 1 ns, directly measured at the device under test.

Figure 3: I-V characteristics of a 20 nm $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NW device in the amorphous (blue circles) and crystalline (red squares) states. The threshold voltage (V_{th}) for the amorphous to crystalline transition and an additional step in the measured current at about 2.25 V are indicated. The inset shows a representative RESET pulse directly measured at the device.

Figure 3 reports the electrical I-V characteristics of a device fabricated using an $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NW with a diameter of 20 nm and a separation between the Ni/Au contacts (L_{gap}) of 700 nm. Below the threshold voltage (V_{th}), two different physical states of the device are present: amorphous (high resistance, RESET) and crystalline (low resistance, SET). Starting from the NW in a SET state (~

50 k Ω), the RESET state (~ 12 M Ω) was enforced by applying a voltage pulse of 100 ns and amplitude of 3 V (corresponding to a current of 60 μ A). The device was then brought to a low resistance state (~ 85 k Ω) during the I-V, once a V_{th} of ~ 780 mV was reached. The initial SET state (~ 50 k Ω) was restored increasing the voltage up to 2.75 V. This SET state was stable and the device resistance remained low as the voltage was swept back to zero. It is important to notice that the SET resistances measured here are about two orders of magnitude smaller than those previously published for In-Sb-Te NWs [16] and comparable to what reported for other phase change NWs, like Ge₂Sb₂Te₅ [9] and GeTe [10]. The remarkably lower resistance values with respect to the previously reported ones [16] might be related to a lower defect density of the studied NWs, or to a lower contribution of the metal/NW contact resistance. It should be noticed that in PCM devices the SET resistances should not be larger than hundreds of k Ω , to ensure a fast and reliable reading [20]. Low resistance values could also explain the lower voltage required for RESET (~ 3 V) compared to the ~ 9.4 V value reported in [16]. This is another crucial aspect, due to the limitations of the voltage range provided by the cell selectors used in PCMs [21]. Our RESET and threshold voltages are also considerably smaller than those reported for In-Sb-Te-based planar cells [14], [15]. The transition from the high resistance amorphous state to the low resistance crystalline state, occurring at V_{th} , is expected to be controlled by the electric field present across the amorphous region. In fact, when a critical value of the field is reached, the resistance of the amorphous phase decreases. In turn, this drop in resistance allows an appreciable current to flow and causes the amorphous phase to reach a material-specific crystallization temperature, thus enabling the SET transition. We estimated the value of the critical electric field (E_{th}) by using the existing models. Since $E_{th} = V_{th}/u_a$, where u_a is the effective length of the amorphized part of the NW, the first step consists in evaluating this length. This can be done by analyzing the I-V curves

of the NWs in the RESET (amorphous) state within the subthreshold range, i.e. for $V < V_{th}$. We used the model proposed in [22], for a conduction limited by the traps at a (constant) distance Δz from each other, where the current is expected to follow the equation:

$$I = 2qAN_{T,tot} \frac{\Delta z}{\tau_0} e^{-(E_C - E_F)/kT} \sinh\left(\frac{qV}{kT} \frac{\Delta z}{2u_a}\right) \quad (1).$$

In equation (1), q is the elementary charge, E_F is the Fermi level, E_C is the conduction band level, A is the cross section of the NW, $N_{T,tot}$ is the integral of the trap distribution in the gap above the Fermi level, τ_0 is the characteristic attempt-to-escape time for the trapped electron, k is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature. The data fitting by equation (1) of the measured subthreshold I-V characteristic of a NW in the RESET state is reported in Figure 4 (a).

Figure 4: (a) Fitting by equation (1) (dashed red curve) of I - V data (black circles) for $V < V_{th}$ with $V_{th} = 0.69$ V, measured on a NW with $L_{gap} = 480$ nm and diameter of 22 nm in the RESET state; the calculated value of $u_a/\Delta z$ is 2.5. (b) $u_a/\Delta z$ dependence of V_{th} (black squares) for several NWs in different RESET states. The dashed red line is the linear fit of the experimental data.

From the fit, the values of $u_a/\Delta z$ were calculated for several NWs in different RESET states. The plot of V_{th} as a function of the $u_a/\Delta z$ values is shown in Figure 4 (b). V_{th} increases linearly with u_a (Δz is constant in the model by [22]), indicating a constant value of E_{th} . From the slope of the linear fit to the data points, the value of E_{th} can be estimated, except for the value of Δz , i.e. $E_{th} \cdot \Delta z = 0.29 \pm 0.02$ V. For a value of $\Delta z = 5$ nm [22], E_{th} is about 60 V/ μm . Such value of E_{th} is comparable to those measured for $\text{Ge}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_5$ in heater-based [23] and “line concept” [24] PCM

cells and for GeTe and Sb₂Te₃ NW-based devices [10]. Figure 4(b) also suggests that only a small fraction of the NW length (a few tens of nm) is amorphized during the RESET operation. Nevertheless, the typical values of V_{th} in our devices are high enough to guarantee a sufficient wide read out window and bit stability against voltage fluctuations.

Interestingly, the I-V curve in Figure 3 shows two current steps during the voltage sweep. The presence of current steps in the I-V curve of planar In₃Sb₁Te₂ PCM cells at voltages larger than the V_{th} has also been reported in [14] and attributed to successive structural transformations of the crystalline state. This is an appealing characteristic of the In₃Sb₁Te₂ alloy in the quest for the development of multilevel memory cell technology.

Figure 5: (a) SET-RESET cycling test of a 22 nm $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NW device. The memory window defined by the resistance difference between the amorphous (blue circles) and crystalline (red squares) states is indicated. (b) Resistance of a 20 nm $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NW device after writing pulses of 100 ns with increasing voltage amplitudes, obtained for initially high (blue circles) and initially low (red squares) resistance states.

Reversible and well reproducible memory switching of the $\text{In}_3\text{Sb}_1\text{Te}_2$ NWs was proved for several devices. Figure 5 (a) shows a SET-RESET cycling test performed on a 22 nm NW device with $L_{\text{gap}} = 480$ nm. Both SET and RESET resistances were measured at 20 mV. For each cycle the amorphous state (blue circles in Figure 5 (a)) was obtained by a RESET voltage pulse of 100 ns

and amplitude of 3.17 ± 0.06 V. The crystalline state (red squares in Figure 5 (a)) was obtained by a d.c. sweep from 0 to 2.5 V. The low resistance state obtained with a d.c. sweep represents the limiting case (“infinite” SET pulse duration) and gives the intrinsic SET state resistance of the device. Figure 5 (a) clearly shows two distinct memory states, with a resistance gap of over two orders of magnitude. The cycling test proved that the memory window was well maintained up to 8 cycles, even without a passivation coating to avoid NW degradation. The average value (calculated over the switching cycles) of the RESET current, converted from the measured amplitude of the pulsed RESET voltage and the device SET state resistance (measured in d.c.), was 41 ± 6 μ A, equivalent to a current density of 13 ± 2 MA/cm²; the corresponding RESET power was 130 ± 20 μ W. These values of RESET current and power are considerably lower than those reported for NWs based on the Ge-Sb-Te system [9], [25]. Lower RESET power in chalcogenide NWs has only been obtained via defect engineering of their microstructure [8]. Fast SET operation was also proved by pulsed voltage. The resistance change of a 20 nm thick NW device, starting from the high resistance state and applying consecutive writing pulses of 100 ns with increasing voltage amplitudes, is shown in Figure 5 (b). A significant resistance decrease was observed above a value of 2.0 V, as a result of the electronic switch of the amorphous phase, followed by Joule-heating-induced recrystallization. The corresponding RESET programming curve, obtained starting from a low resistance state, is also reported. In this case, a large resistance increase was observed above 2.9 V, due to the amorphization in the NW. The non-monotonic behavior of the resistance around 2.9 V could be related to a competition between amorphization and crystallization processes [26].

In conclusion, we demonstrated the phase change behavior of ultra-thin In₃Sb₁Te₂ NWs with low programming voltage, current and power consumption. This makes them suitable

building blocks for the realization of devices with better performances than the most recent heater-based PCMs with confined cell scheme [27], [28]. Our study also establishes the possibility to verify the long-term data retention and multilevel properties of In-Sb-Te based nano-sized PCM cells.

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